

A STUDY OF THE TENSILE FAILURE MODE OF LASER MICRO-PERFORATED CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY: A study has been made of the tensile failure of carbon fibre composites based on two different thermoplastic matrices. The introduction of an array of fine holes into such materials is of interest in view of the consequent improvements in formability, provided this can be achieved without unacceptable degradation of properties. It is found that a reduction in tensile strength of around 25% is induced in unidirectional composites by the presence of an array of fine holes designed to reduce the fibre length to 20 mm. The fracture path in perforated specimens runs between the holes along the fibre axis - ie parallel to the direction of loading. Lesser reductions in strength were observed with fewer holes or with other stacking sequences. The cracking parallel to the applied load was less pronounced in these specimens, although it still occurred to some degree. It has been established that this form of cracking is caused by shear stresses which peak at the surface of the holes. Computed values of these stresses are appreciably above the critical values for these systems. This information will be useful in designing hole patterns for optimisation of the microperforation process.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic Composites, Microperforation, Laser Processing, Tensile Strength, FEM Modelling, Failure Criteria, Shear Failure.

INTRODUCTION

A major problem with long fibre reinforced thermoplastics is that the formability is strongly impaired by the presence of the fibres. Attempts to form such material, during or after consolidation, tend to cause major microstructural defects such as wrinkling, buckling or fracturing of groups of fibres [1,2]. A promising approach to this problem is to break up the fibres in a controlled manner, such that the formability is enhanced, but leaving the average fibre aspect ratio sufficiently high for the stiffness and strength to be relatively unimpaired.

Several fibre fragmentation methods have been proposed, giving products ranging from chopped strand mat to Du Pont's Long Discontinuous Fibre™ (LDF) material [3-5]. The chopped strand mat compounds tend to have very short fibres in a planar random orientation. This limits the fibre content and results in mechanical performance well below that of the corresponding long fibre material. LDF is manufactured by a complex stretch-breaking process, prior to resin infiltration. This leads to a high volume fraction (58vol%) composite, with fibres of varyin length (typically ~50 mm). Chang [3] found that LDF materials showed excellent mechanical properties - comparable with continuous fibre composites. Schuster [6] extended the work of Chang to include mechanical testing of deformed LDF, using a hot press

integrated within a tensile testing machine. Schuster reported an increase in static strength for very small strains (up to 3%), attributed to an improvement in fibre alignment. However, there are various practical drawbacks associated with the production process which may inhibit widespread use of LDF material.

Recent studies [7,8] have outlined the development of a novel fibre fragmentation process, based on use of a laser beam to break fibres up in a controlled manner. This has certain important advantages over the LDF process, including no requirement to modify the pre-preg manufacturing process and considerable versatility with regard to the spatial distribution of fibre fracture sites. It has been shown [8] that the loads needed to deform such laser perforated material are considerably lower than those required for corresponding unperforated laminates. There is, however, concern about the effect of the arrays of fibre fracture sites produced by laser perforation on the mechanical properties of the composite. The current paper presents an investigation of the failure characteristics exhibited by microperforated carbon fibre composites under tensile loads.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The Perforation Process

Two composite systems have been studied. These are (a) PEEK-61vol%C (APC-2) and (b) PPS-57vol%C. Details of these systems are available in the literature [9,10]. The laser microperforation process, the principle of which was developed by Integrated Materials Technology Ltd [11], was applied to pre-pregs of these materials. This process involves moving the pre-preg past a laser head which is being fired at pre-determined intervals. Micrographs of single holes, and a schematic of the pattern of holes, produced in this way are shown in Fig.1. For the perforation operation applied to the specimens described here, the pattern parameters indicated in Fig.1(c) had the values shown in Table 1. Two fibre lengths were chosen for the current work: 20 mm and 100 mm. A small degree of overlap between adjacent holes is necessary to ensure that all fibres become cut to the selected length. However, the hole pattern was designed to ensure that the zones of stress concentration adjacent to individual holes did not overlap at all when the material was loaded parallel to the fibre axis.

Although the laser beam was circular in section (with a diameter of about 80 μm), the holes are approximately ellipsoidal as a result of the continuous relative motion between beam and specimen. (The distance travelled during the firing period of the laser was about 100 μm .) It should also be noted that the holes exhibit a considerable degree of taper - see Fig.1(b). The diameters quoted in Table 1 are average values through the thickness of the pre-preg. The severity of this taper is dependent on the thermal properties of the pre-preg and the laser firing conditions.

It can be seen in Fig. 1(b) that the hole was completely refilled with resin during consolidation. Although the filled hole will still act as a stress concentrator (since the resin is very compliant), this means that the resin will afford environmental protection to the fibres. A further point is that some fibre swelling can be seen adjacent to the hole. This is presumably due to inelastic changes in the fibre structure, or possibly entrapment of gas, induced by thermal shock and exposure to very high local temperature.

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of single holes in APC-2, showing (a) free surface of a pre-preg after perforation and (b) section through a consolidated laminate. (c) Schematic plan of an array of holes.

Table 1. Perforation pattern parameters

Pattern Code	Diameter (\perp fibre axis) D_x (μm)	Diameter (\parallel fibre axis) D_y (μm)	Pitch (\perp fibre axis) P_x (mm)	Pitch (\parallel fibre axis) P_y (mm)	Overlap (\perp fibre axis) δ_x (μm)	Fibre length L_y (mm)
L20	150	80	1.0	2.0	50	20
L100	150	80	2.2	4.54	50	100

Mechanical Testing

Once perforated, the pre-preg material was consolidated into uni-directional, UD, cross-ply ($0/90^\circ$), and quasi-isotropic ($[0/+45/-45/90]_s$), QI, laminates. These laminates were made from 8 plies of pre-preg, each being 0.125mm (APC-2) or 0.140mm (PPS-C) in thickness. Consolidation parameters were based on those recommended by the pre-preg manufacturers [9,10].

After consolidation, tensile test specimens of length 250 mm, width 20 mm and thickness ≈ 1 mm were cut from the laminates. For the UD material, off-axis specimens were produced with the long axis at selected angles to the fibre direction. Specimen dimensions conformed to those set down in the CRAG testing procedures [12]. Specimens were end-tabbed using 50 x 22 x 1.6 mm aluminium tabs, bonded using Redux 420 adhesive. This is a two-part epoxy-based adhesive, cured in a heated platen press for 2 hours. For off-axis loading, slightly smaller specimens (150 x 20 x 1 mm) were used, due to limits on material availability. Strain gauges (5 mm Kyowa) were used to obtain failure strain and modulus data.

Mechanical testing was carried out using a 100 kN Schenck screw-driven testing machine. Tensile test samples for UD, 0/90° and QI specimens were loaded at a strain rate of $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, load and strain data being logged on a Macintosh via a MacLab data acquisition unit. The majority of the tests were repeated about 5-8 times and appropriate average values were calculated.

RESULTS

Elastic Constants

Strain gauges placed parallel to the fibre direction were used to determine the axial Young's modulus, E_1 , of both perforated and unperforated material. This was calculated from the initial gradient of the true stress / true strain plot. Data for PPS-C laminates are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the moduli of the perforated materials are almost identical to those of the corresponding unperforated material, even for the shortest fibres. This is hardly surprising, since the aspect ratio of the 20 mm fibres is almost 3000. With this large aspect ratio, full load transfer [13] is expected to occur, giving a stiffness similar to that for continuous fibres.

Table 2. Young's Modulus data for perforated and unperforated PPS-C Laminates.

Specimen Code	Young's modulus $E_1 \pm \sigma_n$ (GPa)	Specimen Code	Young's modulus $E_1 \pm \sigma_n$ (GPa)	Specimen Code	Young's modulus $E_1 \pm \sigma_n$ (GPa)
UD-L ∞	133.3 \pm 6.23	0/90-L ∞	67.87 \pm 2.35	QI-L ∞	45.09 \pm 0.91
UD-L100	136.3 \pm 2.77	0/90-L100	67.63 \pm 1.44	QI-L100	45.01 \pm 0.68
UD-L20	134.2 \pm 5.60	0/90-L20	60.94 \pm 3.44	QI-L20	45.00 \pm 1.77

Strength of Laminates

Failure strength data for APC-2 laminates are shown in Fig.2. The measured strengths of unperforated material (plotted at a fibre length corresponding to the specimen length) are broadly consistent with data in the literature [9,14]. It can be seen that introduction of the perforations has had a significant effect in reducing the strength of the unidirectional material, with a drop of about 25% effected by reducing the fibre length to 20 mm. The degradation on reducing the fibre length from 100 mm to 20 mm suggests that it is not simply the stress-concentrating effect of isolated holes which is responsible for the strength reduction, but rather that some interaction can occur between them which facilitates failure. This was confirmed by several experiments in which single holes of similar diameter to the laser perforations were drilled in the material. The resulting reductions in strength were small and were in all cases significantly less pronounced than in specimens with arrays of holes. It may also be noted that the observed reductions in strength on perforation are appreciably less marked for the cross-ply material, although still detectable.

Figure 2 Failure Strengths of APC-2 Laminates. (Data for unperforated laminates have been plotted at a fibre length corresponding to the specimen length of 250 mm).

Corresponding data for the PPS-C material are shown in Fig.3. These show broadly similar trends to the APC-2 results. There is a significant reduction in the failure stress as the fibre length is reduced, ie as the density of microperforations is increased. However, it is noticeable that only a small reduction from the long fibre case is observed when the fibre length is 100 mm, particularly for the UD material. This suggests a slightly different type of interaction between the holes compared with the APC-2, possibly related to differences in interfacial bond strength or matrix properties.

Figure 3 Failure Strengths of PPS-C Laminates. (Data for unperforated laminates have been plotted at a fibre length corresponding to the specimen length of 250 mm).

Fractography

Study of the fracture surfaces from UD specimens clearly suggested an interaction between individual holes. It is clear from SEM micrographs such as that of Fig.4(a) that there is a strong tendency for cracks to run between perforations, parallel to the applied load and fibre axis. A characteristic zig-zag crack path is thus produced, of the form shown schematically in Fig.5. Each layer of pre-preg in a laminate exhibited its own independent zig-zag pattern of this type. This involves only failure of the matrix material or fibre-matrix interface and no fibre fracture is necessary. It is not, however, immediately obvious how the applied tensile load can give rise to stresses within the specimen which could cause this mode of failure.

Figure 4. Micrographs showing fracture profiles from perforated APC-2 laminates. (a) SEM of fragment from the centre of a UD specimen, and (b) Optical micrograph of a 0/90° laminate. The loading axis was vertical in both cases.

Figure 5 Schematic depiction of the fracture path followed in UD laminates, with the laser-drilled holes being linked up by extensive cracking parallel to the fibre direction.

A tendency for this mode of failure to occur was also apparent in the 0/90° and QI laminates. This can be seen in Fig.4(b). However, in these cases the cracking parallel to the loading axis in 0° plies is largely suppressed by the presence of transversely-oriented fibres in adjacent plies. The extensive fracture surface areas normal to the loading direction, seen in the UD specimens, were therefore absent in these materials, although debonded bundles of fibres, terminating in a laser-drilled perforation, could clearly be seen.

Off-Axis Testing.

To investigate the zig-zag failures seen in the UD laminates, more information was needed regarding the transverse and shear properties of the composite. A series of off-axis tests was therefore undertaken, aimed at establishing the shear and transverse strengths of unidirectional material relative to the fibre axis, τ_{12u} and σ_{2u} . A number of tensile test coupons were cut from an 8-ply laminate of unperforated UD APC-2. Specimens were cut at 0°, 30°, 60° and 90°, with at least three specimens per orientation. Specimens were end-tabbed as before, using aluminium tabs and Redux adhesive, and loaded to failure. The results are plotted in the form of measured strength against loading angle, ϕ , in Fig.6.

These data can be used to generate estimates for τ_{12u} and σ_{2u} , by using either the maximum stress or the Tsai-Hill failure criterion. In each case, a best fit curve is obtained for the experimental data. The equations [15] governing the maximum stress criterion - equations (1a), (1b) and (1c) - and those for the Tsai-Hill failure criterion - equation (2) are given below.

$$\sigma_{\phi^*} = f(\sigma_{1u}, \cos^2\phi) \quad (1a)$$

$$\sigma_{\phi^*} = f(\sigma_{2u}, \sin^2\phi) \quad (1b)$$

$$\sigma_{\phi^*} = f(\tau_{12u}, \sin\phi \cos\phi) \quad (1c)$$

$$\sigma_{\phi^*} = \text{bbc}[(f(\cos^2\phi(\cos^2\phi - \sin^2\phi), \sigma_{1u}^2) + f(\sin^4\phi, \sigma_{2u}^2) + f(\cos^2\phi\sin^2\phi, \tau_{12u}^2))^{-1/2}] \quad (2)$$

The value of σ_{2u} can be obtained directly as the measured strength at $\phi = 90^\circ$, which is about 84 MPa. Since the data for $\phi = 60^\circ$ lie almost exactly on the transverse failure curve, only the data for $\phi = 30^\circ$ can be used to estimate τ_{12u} . This leads to a prediction of $\tau_{12u} = 73$ MPa if the maximum stress criterion is used, and $\tau_{12u} = 80$ MPa if the Tsai-Hill criterion is used. A more detailed study, with many more data points in the range 10-30°, of the off-axis properties of APC-2 has been carried out by Cervenka [16] and his results led to an estimate of $\tau_{12u} = 78$ MPa; this correlates well with the results presented here.

Figure 6 Measured strength data from off axis testing of APC-2 UD Laminates, together with predicted variations obtained using the maximum stress and Tsai-Hill criteria.

MODELLING OF STRESS FIELDS AROUND HOLES

Mesh Generation

An ABAQUS finite element model was set up in order to study the stress fields generated around the holes when a uniaxial load was applied in the fibre direction. Quadratic plane stress elements with 8 nodes were used for this analysis. Figure 7 shows the mesh. This represents three circular holes in an anisotropic continuum. There has been no attempt to model fibres and matrix separately. This also means that the model does not consider any differential Poisson contractions that may occur, which might give rise to transverse tensile stresses across the fibre/matrix interface. The holes have a diameter of 150 μm and are displaced from each other by 2 mm in the 1-direction and 100 μm in the 2-direction. This geometry corresponds to the perforation pattern used here for the fibre length of 20 mm. In this model, the fibre direction, i.e. the stiff direction, is the 1-direction. The left hand column of nodes was fixed, and a uniaxial tensile load of 2000 MPa was applied to the nodes on the right hand edge of the mesh in the 1-direction. The introduction of resin into the holes does not significantly affect the computed stress distributions.

Figure 7. Mesh used for Finite Element Modelling of stress field around microperforations.

ANALYSIS OF STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS

The distributions of the σ_{22} and τ_{12} stresses are of particular interest, since they are expected to be responsible for cracking parallel to the fibres and hence to control the zig-zag failure mode seen in the perforated unidirectional composites. Study of the σ_{22} stresses revealed that they were all very low. This is expected, since there is no obvious origin for such stresses in a single ply when the composite is treated as a continuum (so that differential Poisson contraction between fibre and matrix is neglected). In practice, tensile σ_{22} stresses could arise in 0_ plies within a laminate, as a result of differential Poisson contraction between plies, but this is clearly not responsible for the observed fracture mode of the unidirectional laminates.

Figure 8. Distribution of τ_{12} stress around a single perforation in a UD laminate loaded parallel to the fibre axis.

The distribution of τ_{12} stresses is given in Fig.8. This shows that significant shear stresses arise on planes parallel to the applied load, particularly those which are close to being tangential to the hole. These shear stresses arise as a direct consequence of the stress concentrating effect of the hole, since the high σ_{11} stresses borne by sections passing close to the hole must fall off rapidly in sections which pass through the hole. Furthermore, the shear stresses peak at the hole surface, where they are likely to initiate propagation of the cracks which link the perforations. The predicted peak value is around 400 MPa, with values of over 100 MPa persisting to distances of about 2 hole diameters. In practice, the peak shear stress might be expected to be somewhat less than this as a result of some load sharing with adjacent plies - in which the holes would in general not be located in the same positions in the 1-2 plane. On the other hand, the actual holes are elliptical in section, with the major axis in the

2-direction, so that the σ_{11} stress concentration, and hence the peak τ_{12} stress, would be higher than for circular holes. In any event, comparison between the computed τ_{12} stresses and estimated values for τ_{12u} of around 70-80 MPa indicates that it is very likely that the observed tendency for extensive cracking parallel to the fibres in 0° plies arises in this way.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The tensile strength of two carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite systems has been measured with and without arrays of fine holes produced by laser drilling, in unidirectional, cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates. The hole patterns were designed to break the fibres up into selected lengths, while minimising the degree to which stress concentration zones around them would overlap.
2. Significant reductions in strength resulted from incorporation of the holes, particularly when the hole density was increased so as to reduce the fibre length. This effect was more pronounced for the unidirectional composites than for the other lay-ups. There were only minor differences between the behaviour of the two composite systems.
3. The reduction in strength is largely attributed to interaction between individual holes in such a way that fracture occurred on planes parallel to the fibre axis, along the direction of loading, so as to link up the perforations without needing to fracture any fibres.
4. The stresses responsible for this mode of failure are shear stresses on planes parallel to the loading axis, which reach a peak at the surface of the hole. Computation of these shear stresses has been carried out using FEM.
5. Experimental measurements have been carried out on unperforated unidirectional composite material in order to establish the transverse and shear strengths and also to investigate the failure under mixed mode loading. Comparison between measured shear strengths and computed shear stress distributions has confirmed that these shear stresses are likely to be responsible for the observed mode of failure and hence for at least a significant proportion of the observed loss in strength of the laminates. The implications of this for optimisation of perforation patterns are currently under study.

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